

ON HABERMAS, MARCUSE, AND THE RELEVANCE OF THE CRITIQUE OF TECHNOLOGICAL RATIONALITY TODAY

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ABSTRACT

This the article examines the political status of technology through the lens of the perspectives of Herbert Marcuse and Jürgen Habermas, arguing that technology constitutes a historically situated social form of power organization . Starting from a critique of the illusion of technical neutrality , an ideological mechanism that naturalizes domination in technologically advanced societies , the text analyzes How Habermas depoliticizes technology by inscribing it within a cognitively instrumental interest of anthropological basis , separating it from the normative sphere and confining critique to the communicative correctness of systemic effects . In contrast , Marcuse politicizes technology by conceiving it as a technological *a priori* , that is , as a material grammar that precedes and conditions the field of the possible , functionally integrating individuals into the existing order . Drawing on the mediation of Andrew Feenberg , the article demonstrates that technology can be reopened to social contestation through the notion of technical code , which reveals how dominant values and interests crystallize in artifacts and systems, naturalizing contingent decisions as rational demands . Subsequently , contemporary diagnoses of platform capitalism are mobilized to show how technological rationality intensifies and spreads in digital regimes, operating as a ubiquitous environment for the management of life . It is concluded that emancipation requires effective mastery of the material codes and processes of technology , as well as concrete contestation over its design, a condition for ensuring that political imagination is not reduced to the administration of the existing technology thus reveals itself as an arena in which what human beings can be is decided , rather than as an inevitable destiny .

Keywords: Technique . Technological Rationality . Herbert Marcuse. Jürgen Habermas. Platform Capitalism .

INTRODUCTION

The belief in the neutrality of technology has become one of the most effective ways of naturalizing domination in technologically advanced societies. Under the guise of efficiency and supposed objectivity, considered the fruits of inevitable progress, technical systems present themselves as purely instrumental means, external to normative disputes and indifferent to the power asymmetries that structure their own genesis and social use. However, insofar as technology organizes rhythms of life, patterns of conduct, forms of work, regimes of visibility, and horizons of experience, it can no longer be conceived as a tool serving pre-determined ends, since it operates with historically determined rationality, structuring the totality of social life and converting particular criteria of domination into seemingly universal requirements for functioning.

In this sense, the debate on the ontological status of technology between Herbert Marcuse and Jürgen Habermas remains relevant and transcends the status of an internal divergence within the Frankfurt School. This clash brings together two antagonistic modes of understanding the very relationship between rationality and emancipation. Marcuse insists that modern technology is neither an anthropological destiny nor the expression of a cognitive-instrumental interest of the species, but the historical crystallization of a specific social project, in which the imperatives of capital and hegemonic forms of control are inscribed. Habermas, in turn, tends to preserve technology as a formally neutral domain of instrumental action, separate from the field of normative struggles and, therefore, protected against substantive criticism.

That being said, this article argues that technology is a historically situated social form of power organization, thus distancing itself from conceptions that view it as an invariable attribute of the human species or a trans-historical formal rationality. Furthermore, it argues that Habermas depoliticizes technology by converting it into a neutral anthropological datum, while Marcuse takes the opposite approach. Therefore, it is objected that the core of the Marcusean position should be preserved and radicalized.

To this end, a qualitative approach of a theoretical-conceptual nature is adopted, based on the comparative analysis of primary sources and the critical reconstruction of paradigmatic debates. The procedure consists of confronting the positions of Habermas and Marcuse regarding the status of technology, subjecting them to an immanent reading from which their premises and internal tensions are extracted. Next, Andrew Feenberg's mediation is used as a key to overcoming the initial polarization and providing the critique with adequate analytical tools. Finally, the framework thus constructed is mobilized to interrogate contemporary

configurations of technological rationality, with the help of authors who, following the Frankfurt School tradition, offer diagnoses of the platform capitalism of our times. It is, therefore, a research that operates on the level of concepts, thus aiming to illuminate concrete historical transformations.

The aim, therefore, is to reinsert the critique of technology at the center of social theory, as one of its decisive material conditions, given that it is one of the main axes of social dispute in contemporary societies.

Habermas and the Neutralization of Technology

Habermas's distinction between instrumental action and communicative action constitutes the core of the philosopher's theoretical architecture and the point from which his understanding of technology is organized. Communicative action is reserved the status of normative mediation of social life, while instrumental action is relegated to the domain of technical efficiency. Habermas thus establishes a division that, although analytically fruitful, has the collateral effect of structurally depoliticizing the material infrastructure of society. In this framework, technology appears as a necessary functional means, governed by criteria of control, not as a field traversed by discontinuities and asymmetries of power.

The problem of domination, shifted to the level of communicative pathologies in the lifeworld in Habermas's theory, isolates technical systems from the reach of critique. This creates a functional dualism in which instrumental rationality is treated as inevitable, while communicative rationality is burdened with the task of guaranteeing legitimacy and emancipation. Consequently, the very technical materiality of domination becomes opaque, functioning as an unthematized backdrop to social life.

The operation deepens when Habermas conceives of technology as an expression of a generic cognitive-instrumental interest of the human species. Inscribed under the rubric of a transcendental anthropology, technology is subtracted from concrete history. The philosopher's opinion is unequivocal in this regard:

Technical cognitive interest is rooted in the anthropological constitution of labor. It is oriented towards expanding the power of technical control over natural processes. Empirical-analytical sciences respond to this interest by providing knowledge that allows for the technical control of processes according to rules. (HABERMAS, 2014, pp. 214–215).

Habermas acknowledges the existence of the colonization of the lifeworld by systems, in which instrumental rationality, mediated by capital, invades normative spheres, generating reification and erosion of social integration. Thus, relying on communicative action as a counterpoint and not on a qualitative reconfiguration of technical rationality itself, the author dehistoricizes technology and dissolves its political character into an abstract evolutionary necessity. The difference between a technology oriented towards domination and a technology oriented towards emancipation becomes, in this horizon, secondary, since the instrumental core remains untouched.

Furthermore, although the philosopher's work is permeated by internal tensions, such as Habermas's intention to protect the normative sphere from technical colonization, the unintended effect of his theoretical architecture is the cooling of political conflict, which is thus sidelined from its technical form to the discursive uses that are made of it, leaches the possibility of an immanent critique of the material devices that structure human sociability.

Rejecting the possibility of a qualitative transformation of technical rationality, Habermas preserves the existing form of technology as the implicit horizon of the possible. Emancipation comes to be conceived primarily as a communicative correction of the systemic effects of modernization, and not as a reconfiguration of the very technical means through which this modernization takes place. Technology is thus naturalized in its concrete historical form, while critique is confined to the sphere of discursive legitimation and *ex post normative regulation*.

Habermas's theory thus contributes to the stabilization of a form of structural conformism that accepts existing mechanisms as unavoidable. Politics is reduced to the management of pre-existing systems, and social transformation is driven by consensus processes around means whose form is not questioned. In this scenario, technology operates as a device to stifle political imagination.

Beyond the excessively formal nature of the conception, there is also a critical disarming effect. By reducing technology to the status of a neutral domain of instrumental action, Habermas excludes from social theory precisely the elements that, in modern societies, most strongly structure power relations, such as regimes of visibility and horizons of experience. The neutralization of technology thus becomes the emptying of the very possibility of a politics of technology, leaving only a politics with The technique, that is, the discursive regulation of means whose form remains immune to major criticism.

MARCUSE AND THE POLITICIZATION OF TECHNOLOGY

In direct opposition to Habermas, Marcuse returns technology to the realm of history by conceiving it as a socio-historical project. In this view, technology does not appear as a functional extension of human capabilities, but as a materialized form of a specific power arrangement, a particular social rationality, and a historical regime of production, control, and administration of life. Machines, systems, and infrastructures are not, for Marcuse, neutral means, but repositories of normative choices stemming from dominant interests that are objectified in technical structures and come to operate as second nature.

With this shift, the question ceases to be considered in terms of the adequacy between means and ends and begins to be formulated at the level of the social constitution of rationality. Technological reason is the hegemonic matrix for the organization of social life, not merely subsumed to execute pre-given ends. It therefore participates in the production of these purposes, producing and managing the very demands to which it later presents itself as the inevitable solution.

In this context, Marcuse introduces the notion of *a technological a priori*, based on the fact that technology precedes and conditions the very definition of what is possible to achieve. This concept thus highlights how technological rationality imposes itself as an objective grammar of domination. Marcuse's critique breaks with the idea that modern domination is exercised solely through external coercion or ideology in the classical sense, instead insinuating itself immanently within the very devices of technical rationalization that organize daily life. The functional integration of technology transforms potential tensions and resistances into elements incorporated into the system, neutralizing social negativity even before it explicitly manifests itself.

Thus, despite all change, the domination of man by man remains the historical *continuum* that links pre-technological Reason and technological Reason. The society that designs and carries out the technological transformation of nature alters the basis of domination, gradually replacing personal dependence with dependence on the “objective order of things,” which, despite being the result of domination, functions as a naturalized condition of social life. Technological rationality protects, and does not cancel, the legitimacy of domination, and the instrumental horizon of reason paves the way for a rationally totalitarian society. (MARCUSE, 2015, pp. 158–159).

In Marcuse's work, technique reveals itself as a form of structural domination, going beyond a mere instrument of domination. It reorganizes the field of possibilities, absorbs alternatives even before they can be formulated as such, and integrates individuals into the

existing order through the managed production of needs and satisfactions, legitimizing the *status quo* by making it functionally indispensable.

Unlike Habermas, Marcuse rejects the separation between technical infrastructure and the normative sphere. There is no formally neutral technique that can simply be "better used" by more rational communication; the very form of the technique already carries a determined political and social content. Therefore, emancipation cannot be thought of merely as a discursive correction of the systemic effects of modernization. It requires a qualitative reconfiguration of the very technical means by which social life is organized.

It should be emphasized that Marcuse's politicization of technology also affects the constitution of subjectivity, given that technological rationality produces one-dimensional individuals whose critical/imaginative faculties are atrophied in favor of performative skills.

Finally, Marcuse oscillates between a historical critique of existing technological rationality and the formulation of normative horizons whose institutional mediation remains undetermined. His idea of a "new science" and a "new technology" appears less as an articulated political program and more as a negative demand, as a rejection of the present historical form of technology as a necessary becoming.

Nevertheless, even with this limitation, the critical scope of his proposal is undeniable and remains relevant today. By politicizing technology, Marcuse breaks both with the illusion of neutrality that sustains technocratic conformism and with theories that shift criticism exclusively to the sphere of communication.

FEENBERG AND THE REOPENING OF THE DISPUTE

Returning to Marcuse's critique of Habermas's postulates, Andrew Feenberg reconstructs technology as a social field of conflict and historical choice in a different key. His perspective, known as critical constructivism of technology, rejects the idea that technical development is founded exclusively on technical efficiency. For Feenberg, this image of an autonomous technical rationality obscures power interests and value criteria that permeate the *design* and social effects of artifacts. The crucial point is that technology does not become political only when applied in social contexts; it is born politically oriented insofar as it teleologically stabilizes certain priorities in its form as if they were objective necessities.

In this sense, Feenberg criticizes the dominant notion that technical efficiency constitutes a self-evident neutral value. This conception presupposes that "successful" technologies emerge from intrinsic superiority, as if the ends themselves were given and as if

performance criteria were natural metrics of instrumental adequacy. However, efficiency does not emerge from a vacuum. Efficiency is oriented *a fortiori* towards some objective, according to some standard, and for the benefit of some institutional arrangement. Thus, what counts as "better performance" involves choices that distribute costs and advantages, define acceptable risks, establish levels of control, and determine which users will have autonomy or be reduced to the condition of operators. The language of efficiency then functions as a rationalizing mask for a social selection of goals and a practical hierarchization of values.

In a way, Feenberg repositions the dispute within the technical form. The politics of technology is therefore not an external addendum. Rather, it is inscribed in the architecture of the artifact, in the logic of its functioning, and in the institutional circuits that make it operative. It incorporates values into the act of design, crystallizing decisions in materials, interfaces, operational standards, safety regimes, surveillance mechanisms, and modes of interaction.

Design choices, often presented as purely rational or scientific requirements, the Feenbergian notion of "technical code" operates as an objectified social grammar, in which dominant interests become the structure of operation. Consequently, contestable decisions become invisible, and historical options are converted into inevitable patterns.

Nevertheless, Feenberg emphasizes the contingent aspect of technical development. The same problem can have different solutions, and technically viable alternatives can be discarded for institutional, economic, or political reasons. *Design*, in this sense, is a field of selection and exclusion. It is within this field that decisions are made about what will be prioritized, what will be accepted as collateral cost, and what will be discarded as unfeasible. The technical form thus appears as a sedimentation of a correlation of forces, not as a direct expression of pure instrumental rationality.

Technology must therefore be understood as a social arena, not limited to the macro level of public policies or state decisions, although it includes this duality. It also manifests itself at the organizational level, in management protocols, work routines, and evaluation regimes that reconfigure behaviors. Feenberg, in this way, gives consistency to a thesis that, in Marcuse, appears as a totalizing denunciation: that technology organizes the field of the possible and does so according to socially defined criteria, naturalized as operational requirements.

The philosopher, however, avoids the conclusion that modern technology constitutes a monolithic block without fissures, emphasizing reappropriations that can alter the social meaning of existing technical systems. Democratizing technology, in this context, means effectively contesting *design criteria*, opening the institutional black box, allowing challenges

to efficiency standards, and reorienting the priorities that structure the material functioning of technologies. In his words:

What human beings are and will become is decided by the form of our tools as much as by the actions of statesmen and political movements. The *design* of technology is, therefore, an ontological decision laden with political consequences. The exclusion of the vast majority from participation in this decision is profoundly undemocratic. (FEENBERG, 2002, p. 31 , **our translation**).

In short, the debate intensifies as a critique of technical neutrality and a shift towards the social contingency of technological rationality. A new perspective emerges in which technology is simultaneously constrained by power relations and potentially subject to emancipatory redescriptions. Technology becomes a space of dispute where different agents negotiate, negate, or affirm diverse ways of living, producing, and interacting with the world.

DIGITAL REGIMES AND THE SPREAD OF TECHNOLOGICAL RATIONALITY

Currently, we observe a mutation in technology that is not limited to the introduction of new devices, nor to the quantitative expansion of processing capabilities. There is a dissolution of the classical technical form into a digital medium that involves experience as an atmosphere. The machine ceases to occupy a delimited place in the productive space and begins to coincide with the very environment in which the triad of perception, communication, and decision-making takes place. Technological rationality, which presented itself as the organizing logic of industrial society, now reappears in a diffuse, yet ubiquitous version, operating through the phantasmagoria of an apparatus whose interface is naturalized.

Digitization generalizes the structure previously analyzed by the philosophers of technology mentioned here, saturating the very fabric of social life with calculating devices that operate in the background while maintaining an elusive appearance of neutrality. Technological rationality, previously concentrated in the delimited spaces of industrial production, now permeates ordinary practices mediated by networks. It now spreads as a continuous environment of data processing that realizes, on a new scale, the *technological a priori* denounced by Marcuse, since technology no longer appears as an object of choice.

Many have envisioned the expansion of cyberspace as a new digital agora, capable of intensifying collective intelligence and dissolving traditional chains of knowledge and power. The belief in the virtualization of technology as a spontaneous vector of democratization, disseminated by authors such as Pierre Lévy, fueled the expectation that global interconnection

would soften structural asymmetries. However, what is historically observed is not the dissolution of hierarchies, but their reconfiguration under new technical bases.

Thus, what emerges from Silicon Valley transhumanism is not a “post-human” self, but an ancient acquaintance, the aristocrat turned cybernetic whose head, severed in 1789, has sprouted again. The confidence in technology as a means to create more freedom, more democracy, and less subjugation is once again refuted by its truly distressing “effective results” of reproducing power relations. (LAZZARATO, 2020, p. 217).

Therefore, there is no weakening of technological rationality. On the contrary, what is observed is its intensification. Calculation ceases to be merely an instrument for organizing work and becomes an organizing principle of experience. Platforms structure temporalities, classify relevance, distribute attention, and hierarchize presences. What appears as personalized convenience is, simultaneously, an operation of sorting and filtering. The horizon of the possible is silently delimited by systems that select what can emerge as visible or profitable.

Srnicek (2018) characterizes platform capitalism as a new phase in the realization of capital, highlighting that the core of contemporary technocracy lies in the capture and exploitation of data as a strategic resource. The author emphasizes that platforms, proprietary infrastructures that define access rules and interoperability standards, are also not neutral intermediaries. among users. In these contexts, digital technology then appears as a driving force for centralization that transforms intermediation into structural domination.

Han (2022) offers an additional key by stating that every decisive media shift establishes a new structuring regime of power relations. In this regime, sovereignty shifts to those who control information flows in real time. Digital technology favors a form of domination that dispenses with the explicit negativity of coercion. As a strategy, it incorporates freedom into the performance circuit, converting self-exposure into a requirement for recognition.

In this scenario, technology, whose materiality resides in the distributed infrastructure of servers, cables, data centers, and mobile devices, acts by producing needs and managing satisfaction in a way that functionally integrates behaviors. It no longer depends exclusively on the factory or mass media, although these exist as arms of capital. It becomes immaterial without ceasing to be materially effective. Its strength no longer rests on the tangible machine, but on the invisible architecture that structures experience. The technical apparatus dissolves into the digital environment, while its effectiveness looms large as a tacit condition of the possibilities of human experience.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Exploring the debate about the political status of technology in an effort to restore the political density of what technocratic ideology presents as an instrument leads to a diagnosis that, however lucid, cannot be the final gesture of critical thought. Technology is contested, however, it is necessary to ask: Contested in the name of what? What other form could a technology take that is not intended as an instrument of domination?

The answer does not lie in closed programs, which would reintroduce the very rigidity that is being fought against. Rather, it rests on the explication of negative criteria, of demands that the existing order cannot satisfy without revealing its limits. Namely, a technology oriented towards care and not profit; that prioritizes the common good against digital enclosure; that slows down instead of performing. Such benchmarks are not formulas, but directions for the gaze, guidelines for the re-signification of political imagination.

The greater difficulty, however, lies elsewhere, and the critical tradition does not always address it satisfactorily. It is not enough to desire an emancipatory technique; it requires mastery of the codes, languages, and material processes that constitute the technique. These components are not accessories added to political will; they are an effective condition for any qualitative transformation. Such mastery is currently monopolized by the same institutions that reproduce the dominant rationality. Therefore, breaking this cycle is not a task that theory can accomplish alone. However, neither can it retreat from the need to name the necessary alliance between social movement, insurgent technical knowledge, and research committed to the public interest as a condition for ensuring that the debate over *design* does not become reduced to participatory rhetoric without a material basis.

Ultimately, what remains is to assert that technology is the arena in which what human beings can be is decided, not destiny. To denaturalize its neutral appearance, to re-inscribe it in history and conflict, to contest its form—this is what it means, today, to think of emancipation as a material task. What deviates from this is the administration of the existing order.

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